

NGO MICRO FINANCE AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN – A CASE STUDY OF KARNATAKA

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Abstract

In this paper an attempt is made to review the current status of micro finance sector in the state of Karnataka, in terms of potential demand for micro finance services, current level of outreach and supply in relation to the potential, and extent of involvement of various types of institutions. The rural bankers, NGOs and some government functionaries have done splendid work in the development of self-help groups in the state of Karnataka. The state of Karnataka has been a pioneer in the programme of SHG Bank Linkage and is indeed hailed as a laboratory for micro finance innovations. Under the “Stree Shakthi” programme of Government of Karnataka, the Department of Women and Child Welfare is actively involved in the promotion of SHGs. On the other hand the Regional Rural Banks have themselves promoted thousands of SHGs and have credit linked them a commendable service indeed.

Keywords: *NGO, Micro Finance and SHGs.*

INTRODUCTION

Credit is playing a key role in sustaining the development of the rural area. Primary sector will continue to play an important role in the national economy to meet the increasing demand of a growing population and the industrial sector. Rural development thus depends on the amount of credit available in rural areas. Rural banking has become an important segment of the Indian banking system.

After nationalization of banks in 1969, they forced to move towards rural India and open their branches to meet the credit requirements of rural mass. As a result about 50 percent of the bank branches are located in wide spread rural area. The concept of

class banking has changed its dimension and now the concept is mass banking. In the context of rural banking so many steps have been initiated by the Government of India, such as bank nationalization, lead bank scheme, setting up of regional rural banks, creation of NABARD, implementation of service area approach etc.

In unorganized sector indigenous bankers, money lenders are still playing their own role. They provide timely and quick loan facility, but charge high rate of interest varies between 24 percent to 60 percent per annum and even more. In organized sector commercial banks, regional rural banks and cooperatives are meeting the credit needs of the people in rural areas, where nearly 643 million people living in 5.76 lakh villages, out of the total 1027 million people residing in India. Though these institutions are functioning in good number, large number of ruralites is not exposed to and accessed the services offered by them. They are deprived of these services and left behind. The main reasons for this are illiteracy, ignorance, security problem, cumbersome and lengthy procedures followed by the banking institutions etc.

The inability of credit institutions to deal with the credit requirements of the poor effectively has led to the emergence of micro finance or micro credit system. Credit is a crucial input in the process of development. Micro finance provides credit access to poor with no collateral obligations. It encourages savings and promotes income-generating activities. Loans are provided at the market driven rates of interest and peer pressure is used in repayment. Micro finance is carried out through self help groups where poor come together in the range of 10-20 by weekly, fortnightly and monthly meetings through their savings and loaning. It is hoped that through such interventions hitherto uncovered groups are covered with credit and in the process get empowered.

In spite of the massive scale of government intervention towards rural development in India, rural India continues to be reeling under poverty and related problems. Notwithstanding the phenomenal progress seen in the rural credit structure in terms of volume of credit extended, concessionality, coverage of weaker sections including scheduled castes and tribes, almost all institutions constituting the formal part of the rural credit system, suffer from several shortcomings like; (a) Gap between the concern of the policy makers and the quality of the effort

(b) Defects in policy design (c) Infirmities in implementation (d) Loans to the poor were considered as a part of social sector lending and not commercial (e) It was felt that poor were not borrowers but beneficiaries (f) An attitude of 'carefully disguised cynicism

towards the poor' and (g) An attitude of 'poor are not bankable'.

This possibly has been due to the absence of the people's participation in the development programmes and also due to the gap in mutual understanding about perspectives of the supply side (the government, planners, and the bureaucracy) on the one hand and the demand side (the rural poor) on the other. This gap is felt to be filled by the microfinance activity through the Self Help Group approach for sustainable rural development.

The significant feature of the Self Help Groups [SHGs] is that they provide credit to the poor at unsubsidized interest rates besides having relatively low default rates on these loans. SHGs reduce transaction costs of financial institutions that do business with the poor and that of the SHGs themselves. They reduce the cost of financial institutions by acting as intermediary organizations or by providing social collateral that substitute for costly loan appraisals and supervisions. SHG approach has made considerable impact on the development of rural economy in terms of increasing savings of the poor, providing access to credit for the poor at reasonable rates of interest by establishing linkages with the formal financial institutions, improving the production levels and income levels, increasing food security and standard of living, improving asset creation and enhancing income generation activities, augmenting environment sustainability and contributing for the much needed women empowerment. With the enthusiastic roles played by the NGOs, the banks, the public and the governments, over a period of one and a half decade, the SHG approach has transformed into a movement in the rural areas.

Self Help Groups have been receiving greater attention by all the concerned like the Government, NABARD, RBI, Commercial Banks, and RRBs. This innovative form of credit delivery is catching up in a big way in rural areas. SHG movement is leveraging the strength of the formal banking system and flexibility of informal SHGs in providing adequate financial services to the rural poor. The programme has turned in to a social movement with high expansion rates in recent years. Fuelled by competence and enthusiasm at all stakeholder levels, it is expanding rapidly throughout India, including tribal areas.

It is probably the world's largest and most successful micro finance programme for the rural poor-outstanding in its emphasis on self-reliance and local autonomy of the very poor. It is widely felt that there have been perceptible changes in the living conditions of the rural poor mainly on economic side and relatively on social side. It is

with this perceptual background that a detailed study has to be undertaken to find out the economic impact of the Self-Help Groups on the development of women in rural areas.

In this context, it is desirable to generate information and analyses to what extent these Self Help Groups have been able to reduce poverty and vulnerability by; increasing capital / asset formation at the household level, improving household and enterprise incomes, enhancing the capacity of individuals and households to manage risk, increasing enterprise activity within households, expanding employment opportunities for the poor in non-farm enterprises, empowering women and improving the accessibility of other financial services at the community level.

SHG-BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMME IN KARNATAKA

Banking institutions in Karnataka as promoting agencies of SHGs lent micro credit for different activities. The details of micro credit lent by banks in Karnataka are presented in the Table- 1.

TABLE- 1 MICRO-CREDIT LENT BY BANKS IN KARNATAKA (UPTO 2008)

Sl. No	District	SHGs (Number)	financed Amount Lent (Rs.in crore)
01	Bagalkote	2,803	11.47
02	Bangalore Rural	8,030	53.21
03	Bangalore Urban	3,083	18.81
04	Belgaum	9,675	47.80
05	Bellary	9,796	37.71
06	Bidar	10,449	51.86
07	Bijapur	5,760	19.40
08	Chamarajanagar	5,889	25.86
09	Chikamagalur	3,736	16.37
10	Chitradurga	8,717	34.65
11	Dakshina Kannada	23,901	76.29
12	Davanagere	6,268	32.22
13	Dharwad	5,134	21.83
14	Gadag	3,308	14.12

15	Gulbarga	12,279	43.06
16	Hassan	17,374	78.91
17	Haveri	4,797	23.98
18	Kodagu	3,296	12.63
19	Kolar	9,669	42.47
20	Koppal	3,296	12.63
21	Mandya	10,275	44.17
22	Mysore	15,043	69.90
23	Raichur	4,550	16.63
24	Shimoga	7,215	31.57
25	Tumkur	14,682	76.55
26	Udupi	10,042	46.04
27	Uttara Kannada	5,907	28.76
	State Total	2,24,928	994.35

Source: NABARD Reports.

The livelihood needs of the poor – The income and basic needs perspective of poverty:

Cultivating the habit of regular savings and the ability to access them when required through credit not only reduces significantly the vulnerability of the livelihood base of the poor and their dependence, it also enhances human development. It enables them to borrow for urgent needs instead of going to moneylender, which increases their dependency since he/she is often the one who provides them with labour employment at low wages. This, in turn, gives them a degree of freedom to bargain for better wages and working conditions and enables them to build a capital base which hitherto was impossible since the exorbitant interest rates demanded by moneylenders siphoned off all surplus. The feel good factor is evident in a group that has been able to save enough in the group to meet with urgent needs. However, the members of the group need to go further if they are to justify the claim that savings empower people. They need to ensure that savings and credit are managed effectively. SHG bank linkage agency wise cumulative participation Karnataka up to 2007-08 details is presented in Table- 2.

TABLE- 2 SHG- BANK LINKAGE – AGENCY-WISE CUMULATIVE PARTICIPATION IN KARNATAKA UP TO MARCH 2008 (RS.MILLION)

Sl. No	Name of the Agency	No.of SHGs	Bank Loan
01	Commercial Banks	38,605	1,006.79
02	Regional Rural Banks	37,087	1,094.73
03	Cooperative Banks	28,174	734.66
	Total	103,866	2,836.18

Source: NABARD report.

	Commercial Banks	Regional Rural Banks	Cooperative Banks
No.of SHGs	38,605	37,087	28,174
Bank Loan	1,006.79	1,094.73	734.66

The above table clearly shows that all the financial institutions have provided maximum bank loan to self-help groups. Commercial Banks have provided Rs.1,006.79 million and they have formulated 38,605 SHGs in Karnataka up to 2008. Regional Rural

Banks have also played a significant role in providing bank loans to SHGs and even Cooperative Banks also participated in promoting SHGs in Karnataka. Savings made by members are pooled and loaned to one another. SHG members determine the terms and conditions. Loans are provided for all purposes without making the traditional distinction between consumption and income generation. The SHG model provides its members with the space and flexibility to make decisions that are appropriate to each situation. Only private moneylenders lend for such a variety of purposes with minimum pass and paper work; all financial institutions and government schemes lend only for productive purposes. But it is the life events and emergencies that drive the poor to debt traps. It leads also to the diversion of loans taken from formal organizations/government into consumption loans, which they are unable to repay.

TABLE- 3 SHG- BANK LINKAGE – PHYSICAL & FINANCIAL PROGRESS OF PARTICIPATING REGIONAL RURAL BANKS UPTO 2007-08 (RS.MILLION)

Name of the RRB	Cumulative No of SHGs provided with bank loan upto 2007	No.of SHGs provided with bank loan during 2007-08	Cumulati ve bank loan disbursed upto 2007	Bank loan disburs ed during 2007-08	Cumulati ve bank loan disbursed upto 2008
Bijapur Grameena Bank	824	584	25.47	25.73	51.20
Cauvery Grameena Bank	4,114	2,087	119.81	81.56	201.37
Chikmagalur – Kodagu Grameena Bank	120	136	3.84	4.58	8.42
Chitradurga Grameena Bank	3,248	1,369	95.63	46.50	142.13
Kalpatharu Grameena Bank	1,612	1,875	38.96	75.05	114.01
Kolar Grameena Bank	1,203	865	31.42	22.23	53.65
Krishna Grameena Bank	2,409	1,579	70.32	35.84	106.16
Malaprabha Grameena Bank	2,557	2,981	55.33	88.70	144.03

Netravati Grameena Bank	747	194	20.99	5.90	26.89
Sahyadri Grameena Bank	1,420	332	55.04	26.10	81.14
Tungabhadra Grameena Bank	3,152	2,410	76.55	47.84	124.39
Varada Grameena Bank	219	271	4.51	9.84	14.35
Visveswaraya Grameena Bank	304	475	6.96	20.03	26.99
Total	21,929	15,158	604.83	489.90	1,094.73

Source: NABARD Report.

It must be noted, that apart from their savings, SHG members also credit all the interest earned on loans to the group's common fund. Increased lending has been made possible through accessing loan funds from financial institutions, after the SHG- Bank Linkage Programme was launched in 1991-92. Under this programme, there are no subsidies for the asset, yet it has grown, particularly after 1999, and is today the largest micro finance programme in the world. The repayment rates average around 95 percent.

SHG members consider their ability to raise loans from banks and their ability to negotiate with banks directly as a major indicator of increased levels of confidence and self esteem. This provides some insights into SHG members' ability to access finance from mainstream institutions. Many members say that they learnt to sign after joining the group. Although this might seem like a minor achievement to most of us., to SHG members, it seems to be away of gaining acceptance in the „mainstream“ and a source of pride. Many members spoke of how they were previously ashamed to conduct bank transactions, as they used thumb impressions in place of signatures. Only after learning to sign were they comfortable about going to a bank. It was after joining the SHG, that they had gained the confidence of conducting bank transactions on their own, and approaching bank officials for loans.

TABLE-4 CREDIT DISBURSEMENTS TO SHGS UNDER SGSY AND BANK LINKAGE PROGRAMMES (RS.LAKH)

Year	Credit-cum-subsidy disbursed to SHGs under SGSY	Credit disbursed by financial institutions
2005-06	4187.91	1714.00
2006-07	7114.86	3475.39
2007-08	3688.87	7249.50
Total	14991.64	12438.89

Source: 1. SHG-Bank Linkage Programme in Karnataka, NABARD, 2007-08. 2. Ministry of Rural Development 2007-08 for SGSY.

The credit funds provided under the SHG-Bank Linkage Programme in Karnataka compare favorably with the credit disbursed to SHGs in Karnataka under the Swarnajayanti Gram Swarojgar Yojana. It may be recalled that all the previous loan-cum-subsidy programmes of the Central Government for the rural poor, including IRDP and DWACRA, have been merged under SGSY. The SGSY programme is mainly intended to provide loans to groups. Due to various compulsions, individual beneficiaries are also being included in large numbers but they are not considered the primary target. Hence, Table- 5 is shows the loans given to SHGs only.

**TABLE – 5 INCREASED KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF SHG MEMBERS
(PERCENT)**

Particulars	SHG age category	Good Knowledge
Self-help group concept and approach	< 1 year	35
	3 years old	65
	>5 years	90
Banking Knowledge	< 1 year	40
	3 years old	65
	>5 years	95
Health and Sanitation	< 1 year	60
	3 years old	85
	>5 years	95
Family Planning	< 1 year	50
	3 years old	75
	>5 years	70
Income generating programmes	< 1 year	45
	3 years old	75
	>5 years	95
Common properties management	< 1 year	30
	3 years old	25
	>5 years	70

Source: SHG-Bank Linkage Programme in Karnataka, NABARD, 2007-08, Page.102.

The training provided to the SHGs in the initial year and a half, focuses largely on institution building. Apart from this, members also experience an increase in social awareness through capacity building. The study also analyzed whether members felt that their knowledge in these areas had increased and whether and recall. Table- 4.5 indicates that there were significant increases in knowledge and recall as the groups progressed. In all cases it can be seen that members knowledge (and ability to recall this knowledge) increased with the length of time spent as a group member.

Group lending activities are first started in the Southern states of India such as, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Karnataka and Tamilnadu; while West Bengal and Orissa have joined later. Though, Micro finance programmes are mostly organized by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) in India, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) launched a Bank Self help group (SHG) linkage programme in a small way in 1992. The idea of introducing the programme emanated mainly from the successful experiences of the institutions in other countries. The linkage programme under NABARD aims to reach those outside the network of formal credit, improve living standards of poorer sections of rural society and achieve high deposit- credit mobilization and recovery of loans. Karnataka, a pioneer in SHG-Bank Linkage Programme and a recognized laboratory for Micro-Finance Innovations, continues to maintain its leading status in promotion and credit linkage of SHGs. While the NGOs and Women and Child Development Department (WCDD, GoK) have been actively involved in promotion of a majority of the SHGs in the state, all the banks have taken the responsibility of linking these groups with the formal banking system. Over a period of time, some of the RRBs and Co-operative Banks in the state have developed the skill in promoting SHGs on their own and assumed the mantle of Self-Help Promoting Institutions (SHPIs).

The SHG-Bank Linkage Programme registered its progress in the state of Karnataka by leaps and bounds during the year 2007-08. While as many as 1,88,477 SHGs have been promoted by different SHPIs in the state, the cumulative credit linkage by various agencies crossed an impressive ONE LAKH SHGs by 31 March 2008.

A) MODEL-WISE SHG-BANK LINKAGE IN KARNATAKA

The NABARD identified three models of credit linkage of SHGs with banks in Karnataka showed the following trend as on 31 March 2008:

TABLE – 6 MODEL WISE SHG-BANK LINKAGE IN KARNATAKA, 31 MARCH 2008

Model	Description	No. of SHGs Linked	Credit %	Bank Loan (Rs. Million)
1	SHGs formed and financed by Banks	48,528	47	1,425.73
2	SHGs formed by NGOs and formal agencies, but directly financed by banks	33,347	32	819.26

3	SHGs financed by Banks through NGOs	21,991	21	591.19
Total		1,03,866	100	2, 836.18

Source: SHG Bank linkage programme Karnataka 2007-08NABARD.

MODEL I: SHGS FORMED AND FINANCED BY BANKS

In this model, banks themselves take up the work of forming and nurturing the groups, opening their savings accounts and providing them bank loans. Up to March 2008, 47 percent of the total number of SHGs financed was from this category. This is reflecting an increased role of banks in promoting and nurturing SHGs.

MODEL 2: SHGS FORMED BY FORMAL AGENCIES, NGOS AND OTHERS, BUT DIRECTLY FINANCED BY BANKS

This model continues to have the major share, with 32 percent of the total number of SHGs financed up to March 2008. Here, NGOs and formal agencies in the field of micro-finance, act only as facilitators. They facilitate organizing, forming and nurturing of groups, and train them in thrift and credit management. Banks give loans directly to these SHGs

MODEL 3: SHGS FINANCED BY BANKS THROUGH NGOS AND OTHER AGENCIES AS FINANCIAL INTERMEDIARIES

This is the model wherein the NGOs take on the additional role of financial intermediation. In areas where the formal banking system faces constraints, the NGOs are encouraged to approach a suitable bank for bulk loan assistance. This, in turn, is used by the NGO for on lending to the SHGs. In areas where a very large number of SHGs have been financed by bank branches, intermediate agencies like federations of SHGs are coming up as link between bank branch and member SHGs. Other agencies like NBFCs are also coming up to take up this role. The share of cumulative number of SHGs linked under this model upto March 2008 is 21 percent.

B) AGENCY-WISE SHG – BANK LINKAGE

As on March 2008, 3838 branches of 58 banks participated in the SHG-Linkage programme. The broad category –wise number of these banks, total branches participated and their percentage share to the total achievements is indicated below. The data are presented in Table 4.7 explaining the SHG-Bank Linkage progress of the Commercial Banks in Karnataka.

TABLE – 7 SHGS LINKED BY COMMERCIAL BANKS IN KARNATAKA

Year (As On 31 March)	No of Linked	SHG'sBank (Rs. In lakh)	Loan Refinance (Rs. In lakh)
1999	316	42.85	45.00
2000	718	100.15	93.00
2001	391	63.00	64.00
2002	583	91.27	90.00
2003	966	176.34	173.00
2004	1855	543.99	191.10
2005	1566	434.40	396.00
2006	8030	974.24	119.12
2006	8030	974.24	119.12
2007	6562	2113.34	35.75
2008	14925	5687.34	8.26
Total	35912	10227.38	1215.23

Source: SHG Bank linkage programme Karnataka 2007-08 NABARD.

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	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008
■ No of SHG's Linked	316	718	391	583	966	1855	1566	8030	6562	14925
■ Bank Loan (Rs. In lakh)	42.85	100.15	63	91.27	176.34	543.99	434.4	974.24	2113.3	5687.3
■ Refinance (Rs. In lakh)	45	93	64	90	173	191.1	396	119.12	35.75	8.26

FINDINGS

Based on the analysis and discussion in the study of NGO micro finance and socio-economic development of women, the following findings have been drawn:

1. In Karnataka SHGs, managed in an ideal scenario, provide a way of reducing poverty that simultaneously improves the capacity of its members on many levels. It is grounded in participatory decision-making, which creates a sense of ownership among members. This is very different from how many other poverty alleviation/ human development programmes evolve with a top-down system of decision-making and distance from the people most affected by these decisions for the purposes of presenting an alternative approach to sustainable development.
2. The popular size of the each SHG is around 15 to 20 and 80 per cent of SHGs are covered under this category. About 50 per cent of the SHGs out of 60 surveyed SHGs are borrowed loan from Banks. 63 per cent of the SHGs out of 60 surveyed are promoting income generating activities. About 37 per cent of the SHGs are supporting dairy activities.
3. It is evident that the income of the household increased rapidly and resulted in an acquisition of household assets and thereby leading relatively a better life. After joining the group the status of women has been increased.
4. Majority of the members belongs to agriculture work 32 per cent of the members are agriculture land less labourers and 28 per cent of the

members are doing business after availing credit facilities from SHG and Banks.

5. As many as 37 per cent members had their house hold annual income ranging up to Rs. 10,000/-, 36 per cent member household annual income ranging from Rs.10,000 to Rs.20,000. Only 16 per cent members household income ranging from Rs. 20,000 to Rs. 30,000.
6. Nearly 50 per cent of the total members belong to economically poor and belongs to back ward communities. About 36 per cent of the total members belong to SC/ST, as many as 28 per cent OBC and only 16 per cent belongs to minority community.
7. As many as 70 per cent of the total respondents have developed the attitude of involving themselves in social and economic activities after SHG formation. There was remarkable improvement in social empowerment of SHG members in terms of self-confidence, involvement in decision making, better communication etc.
8. The SHG membership is a sense of social commitment that more than 80 per cent members are against habitual drinking and an average 80 per cent of members are inclined to protest against social evils after SHG membership.
9. The members were relatively assertive in confronting with problem situation. There was a fall in the incidence of family violence.
10. The gender consideration is the major factor that prompted people to join SHG.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

In the light of our findings and observations some suggestions are made about effective functioning of NGO controlled microfinance institutions in the socio-economic development of the women. The suggestions are listed as follows:

1. Sustainability is of root significance to micro financing programmes. Sustainability still remains the most concerning aspect of SHG approach for rural development. Banks, which also promote SHGs themselves, such as the RRBs do not have adequate institutional capacity to sustain this role. Further, neither banks nor NGOs take in to consideration the

resources needed to maintain the SHGs structure after promotion and to address the inevitable negative group dynamics on the long run.

2. The attaining financial viability and sustainability is the major institutional challenge for micro finance institutions. Deposit mobilization is the major means for microfinance institutions to expand outreach by leveraging equity. In order to be sustainable, microfinance lending should be based on market principles, because large scale lending cannot be accomplished through subsidies. The microfinance can contribute to solving the problem of inadequate housing and urban services as an integral part of poverty alleviation programmes.
3. Separate National Bank for Women Self Help Groups is required to promote and protect the financial interest of the members.
4. The NGO sector is increasingly pursuing the financial intermediation as one of the effective tools in meeting their social agenda. In this context, the governments, both at the center and the states have an equally important role to play in creating conducive policy environment for the growth of this NGO sector as future micro finance institutions. Here, what is required is suitable policy framework, innovative package of services with timely credit.
5. SHGs may be permitted to issue fixed deposits certificates, Cash certificates and other savings oriented instruments may be under the authorizing of the concerned lead bank in the respective district.
6. The Banks may encourage SHGs to open Saving Bank accounts for different purpose say for education, marriage, capital asset purchase etc. so that the amounts accumulated in the respective account be utilized for the said purpose only. This ensures the SHG members to fulfill their social commitments much better.
7. SHGs to become more meaningful and purposeful should be constantly guided by NGOs with regard to their activities, especially the purposes for which the loans are sanctioned.
8. Literacy programmes including awareness programmes may be taken up seriously by NGOs, Banks, SHG Federation's and Voluntary

Organizations as this component alone can bring success for any socio-economic welfare in the State.

9. Banks and NGOs should provide training to the members of the SHGs in different filed especially in income generating activities. The Banks in the rural areas may be asked to liberal to SHGs with regard to amount of loan with lower interest that can be lent to SHGs.
10. Micro-enterprises was visualized as the logical culmination of the efforts made in mobilizing micro-credit and micro-finance. While micro-credit and micro-finance have achieved a significant level of success, which has been well documented, the actual record of implementation in the sphere of micro-enterprises is less than satisfactory.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that NGO controlled microcredit organizations do not incur lower transactions costs than banks, but they are able to transfer these costs to others – donors and borrowers. We also argued that one important component of high administrative costs was the cost of monitoring so as to ensure regular repayment. The lesson from the microcredit experience is that small scale rural credit is indeed necessary. However, rural credit policy must build on the strengths of the banking system in India as its mainstay. Banks have many advantages over private micro credit organizations as providers of small scale loans. They have advantages of scale; the banking system in India has a reach and spread that NGO controlled microcredit cannot begin to match; banks can cross-subsidies loans; banks are better placed to provide specialized training to their employees in development banking; banks are better placed to coordinate banking activity with development administrations, local governments and SHGs; and banks are better able than private microcredit organizations to offer a wide range of financial services to borrowers. For the state to withdraw from the field and hand over small-scale credit to NGO-controlled microcredit organizations is, in effect, to undermine and weaken a major national asset, the widespread rural banking system.

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